

FOOD RECONGITION SYSTEM USING DEEP LEARNING METHODS

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Abstract

The deep learning has demonstrated its effectiveness and powerful in computer vision, which is used to classify and localize depending on image and has a feature as high accuracy and easiness. In this proposed work, we focus on the improvement of food recognition system for resolve the challenges, which faced in the construction of the system and the main reason for these challenges is an intra class, which are different in ingredients, sizes, shapes, cooking method and occultation's. So, all these different make foods classify is challenge because make high non- linear. This proposed work presents a new approach depending on the latest algorithms of deep learning to develop the food recognition system including classification, localization, segmentation and food volume estimation. Our proposed work has four methods including classification, localization, segmentation and food volume estimation. The classification and localization have three steps. Firstly, the food image enhancement using image processing. Secondly, we improve the algorithm by combination of convolution neural network (CNN) and edge detector method for extract low and high level of features. Thirdly, locate the item of food through the Region Proposal Network (RPN). In the segmentation method, we develop instance segmentation, in order to get the best boundaries for the image food. Finally, we develop CNN to find the food volume estimation in respect of transforms to 3-Dimensional reconstructions (3D) to calculate the calories of image food.

1 INTRODUCTION

Deep learning is the branch of the machine learning, which has received much attention recently because of effectiveness in many filed such as computer vision [1] and neural language processing [2]. The Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) is most important model of deep learning and considered as the state of the art in image recognition and detects object.

It was used in the context of competitions such as the Image-Net Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC). It was started with AlexNet network, which was used by Alex Krizhevsky et al [3]. AlexNet network showed impressive results of use deep convolution neural networks to solve recognition, classification and detection object from image. Through the use of CNN, it was found that the CNN is characterized by high accuracy compared to other algorithm that depends on traditional computer vision techniques [3], which opened the way for researchers used CNN for recognition and detection object [4], by modified few details such as the type and number of layer to locate in the network and used different size of filter and used various techniques of batch normalization and dropout [3]. Despite the inability of the computer for solving many tasks that are considered natural for the human in efficiently and effectively way. However, the development of algorithms and the appearance of the concept of deep learning in the vision of the computer have made it possible to solve these problems. The food recognition system is a significant challenge for recognition system due to many challenges such

as different sizes, shapes and cooking method, which encounter in building food recognition system. As a result, building food recognition system is not an easy task. Although there are many algorithms that solve food recognition system but suffers from poor performance. The images food may contain noise making its blurry. The existing food recognition systems not accurate enough such as in the case where some external factors such as light condition. The image, which contains noisy and blurry also contribute to increase accuracy of the recognition and detection process [5]. As a result, image cleaning depend on image processing is important task. Therefore, there is a need to pre-process images to reduce external factors.

2 PROPOSED WORK

We dedicated this research as explanation of research to build effective food recognition system. In this research, building architecture CNN for classifying and localization each item of food image and find the volume of food image through reconstruction 3D. This research begins with the process flow of the proposed food recognition system as shown in figure 1. The research mainly consists of three phases. The first phase is enhancement image through adaptation image processing method to reduce external factors. The second phase is the building architecture CNN for classifying and localization each item of food image. Finally, find the volume of food image through reconstruction 3D.

Figure 1: Overview of the process flow of the food recognition system.

References

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